

COMMUNITY COLLABORATION AND LEARNING FOR CLIMATE RESILIENCE (COOLER) PROJECT END OF YEAR 2 FINDINGS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The COOLER (Community Collaboration and Learning for Climate Resilience) Project was initiated at the University of Northern Colorado (UNC) in 2023 through a Planning Grant funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation's Cultural Transformation in the Geoscience Community (CTGC) program (award #2228170). It is led by UNC faculty, in collaboration with a community builder, evaluation partner, and student leaders. The three-year project aims to build a learning community comprising UNC students, faculty, and northern Colorado residents, and strengthen climate change education, resilience, and adaptation.

In the second year, COOLER built on the first year's efforts to comprise i) **Region-wide community engagement around climate change resilience**; and ii) **CLimates (COOLER Climate Leadership Institute)**, a pilot program for UNC students and faculty, and local community organizations interested in building climate resilience. CLimates aimed to foster engagement through regularly scheduled cohort meetings, networking within and/or across cohorts, independent project work, and COOLER community events open to the public.

The evaluation partner continued to use a community of practice framework to study how CLimates fostered learning and exchange around climate resilience in Northern Colorado. A qualitative assessment documented how the program helped UNC students, faculty, and organizational partners to engage, learn, and collaborate to address local climate priorities.

Key findings

The deepest engagement occurred within cohorts. Faculty interacted closely with colleagues from different disciplines and learned others' unique take on climate-related work. Students interacted with peers about climate change and learned to engage with people not as motivated to address climate impacts. Organizational partners were connected to other local organizations with similar interests in climate work and learned about each other's role locally.

Professional, personal, and organizational capacities were impacted. Some members in each cohort described how they were able to apply the lessons learned. Faculty started to use insights on climate work to inform their teaching. Student cohort members embraced the role of climate stewards on campus and student leaders enhanced their future career opportunities. Organizational partners expanded their audiences and worked with groups around shared interests.

Learning about climate change and resilience occurred in distinct ways. Faculty learned about multi-disciplinary perspectives on climate change. Organizational partners became familiar with different local organizations' approach to climate-related work. Student cohort members and student leaders grew their climate stewardship skills. Climate resilience was understood to be important on many levels, including personal, social, and biophysical.

Implications for the Future

The CLimates program demonstrated the evolution of a learning community between UNC faculty, students, and organizational partners interested in addressing local climate impacts and advancing environmental and social welfare. The cohort-based model resembled a community of practice that helped members network, learn about others' expertise, and in some cases, apply the learning to inform their own or their organizations' work. Cohorts were empowered to be more effective climate stewards through their distinct roles. Local climate resilience was perceived to be a collective endeavor.

THE COOLER PROJECT

The COOLER (Community Collaboration and Learning for Climate Resilience) Project was initiated at the University of Northern Colorado (UNC) in the summer of 2023 through a Planning Grant funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation's Cultural Transformation in the Geoscience Community (CTGC) program (award (#2228170)).

The project is led by faculty from UNC with expertise in climate science, geoscience, environmental science, education, and professional development leadership, in collaboration with external consultants in the roles of community builder and evaluation partner, and student leaders hired to be part of the leadership team.

Over the course of three years, the project aims to build a learning community that is composed of UNC students and faculty, and northern Colorado community members, and strengthen society-wide climate change education, resilience, and adaptation through community projects and engagement.

UNC faculty work to build connections between climate change themes at a COOLER Faculty workshop.

Focus of the second year

In the first year, the project made observable strides to engage UNC faculty and students about the multiple disciplinary perspectives to understand and address local climate change impacts (Gupta, 2024). The first stage of a community of practice was noted among faculty who were interacting with peers to learn about each other's expertise. Student leaders who worked closely with the faculty leaders and consultants expanded their knowledge, ability, and confidence, to address climate impacts through specific roles. Faculty and students recognized the multiple connotations of 'climate resilience' in Greeley, ranging from social to biophysical dimensions.

During the second year, building on the previous year’s work, additional strides were made to foster deeper connections between members of the COOLER community. This was undertaken by developing a pilot program called the COOLER Climate Leadership Institute (CLimates) for UNC students and faculty, and local community organizations interested in building climate resilience. It aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Prepare UNC students from all disciplines to work with community stakeholders on climate related events, projects, or challenges;
2. Prepare UNC faculty to employ their discipline specific expertise in local climate-related challenges; and
3. Build the capacity of local community organizations to address climate resilience by increasing their access to academic and public resources, and strengthening their connection with other climate resilience practitioners.

Faculty, students, and organizational partners were invited to join three separate cohorts. Each cohort had opportunities to engage in closed sessions with peers within their groups, as well as to interact and work with members of the other cohorts. The program was kick-started by an in-person session on September 14, 2024 to learn about COOLER and the CLimates program, and network with members of the various cohorts.

The main components of the CLimates program included:

- regularly scheduled cohort meetings;
- networking within and/or across cohorts between meetings;
- independent project work, that fostered collaborations with other members; and
- COOLER community events open to the general public.

COOLER PI Sharon Bywater-Reyes (left) and COOLER student community managers share local climate data at the Greeley Farmer’s Market.

CLimates participants also had the opportunity to participate in 'theme teams'. Theme teams were unstructured, self-facilitated meetings where members from any cohort could attend and talk about their areas of interest, and often a "theme" was designated by leadership (e.g., waste or water).

Cohort members were informed about requirements for participation in the CLimates program and reminded about them regularly by project leadership. These requirements included attendance at scheduled meetings, participating in one or two community climate-related events, networking with members from other cohorts, developing collaborative projects, and participation in evaluation activities. Communication to cohort members from project leadership occurred regularly on a weekly basis through an email update, and through a LinkedIn group, where cohort members could also communicate directly with each other.

In addition to the CLimates program, the COOLER project also continued its broad community engagement that had been initiated in Year 1. Across the two years COOLER has evolved to comprise two main programs:

1. **Region-wide community engagement around climate change resilience.** For this public-facing program, we share information about climate change resilience through social media, a quarterly newsletter (120+ subscribers) and COOLER-hosted public events (e.g., a monthly podcast-style Ask Me Anything series and a weekly lecture series at UNC in spring 2025), tabling at public events of other organizational partners, and meetings with potential partners and community stakeholders. Our program activities aim to build community amongst anyone with an interest in Northern Colorado climate resilience by helping them interact with and learn from each other.
2. **Climate Leadership Institute (CLimates).** As described above, this 10-month professional development program brought together a 34-person cohort of students, faculty, and members from local community organizations in Greeley to collaborate on self-led projects that build local climate resilience.

MONITORING PROGRESS

In Year 2, UNC continued to partner with an evaluation consultant to understand how the project builds a multi-stakeholder learning community (comprising students, faculty, and community organizations) to build their knowledge and capacity to tackle climate priorities in Northern Colorado. Similar to the previous year, evaluation in the second year also examined how members of the learning community will:

- Grow their knowledge base about local climate resilient priorities;
- Build agency, self-efficacy, and personal resilience in collaborating on local issues;
- Respectfully engage in exchange and learning; and
- Co-develop community-focused projects to build climate resilience in northern Colorado.

A community of practice (CoP) framework (Wenger, Trayner, & de Laat, 2011) continued to inform the evaluation, where a CoP is defined as “a learning partnership among people who find it useful to learn from and with each other about a particular area”, in this case tackling local climate priorities. Similarly, the evaluation once again assessed how the learning community engaged with others holding distinct interests and expertise (Gupta, Ardan, & Fraser, 2017); appreciated different perspectives on environment-focused work (Fraser, Gupta, & Krasny, 2014); and conceptualized and built a climate resilient community (Cutter et al. 2008; Gupta, LaMarca, Nock, Flinner, & Attaway, 2023).

Year 2 evaluation focus

In the second year, the consultant once again worked closely with the other COOLER team members, including one-on-one with the project PI, to learn more about the evolution and emerging focus of the project. The newly developed CLimates program was the main focus, so that the evaluation aimed to understand how the three cohorts engaged, learned, and collaborated within and across cohorts. The audiences for the evaluation were:

- UNC faculty members;
- UNC students;
- Organizational partners (representing local community groups who participated in the Climate Conversations workshops initiated in the Fall of 2023 and continued in spring of 2024); and
- Student leaders hired to join the COOLER leadership team in the second year.

Similar to the first year, a developmental evaluation approach (Patton, 2011) was used, emphasizing a collaborative approach. Similarly, interactions with all stakeholders were attentive to their circumstances and expertise, and involved close observations, careful listening, and facilitation of reciprocal exchange of knowledge (Pipi, Cram, Hawke, Hawke, Huriwai, Mataki, T., et al. 2004; Smith, 2005).

METHODOLOGY

Study design and recruitment

The evaluation was conducted through a set of virtual focus groups with the four groups of audiences. Aligned with the goal of the learning community to foster close engagement within cohorts, focus groups were deemed most useful as the evaluation method. Focus groups would enable a close understanding of the participants' lived experience by closely examining their perspective of the topic or phenomena of interest while interacting with peers (Van Manen, 2002). The topic of interest, in this case, was climate knowledge, action, and resilience in Northern Colorado.

Semi-structured focus group protocols and recruitment materials were developed in close collaboration with the COOLER project team. Invitations to the focus group were emailed by the project Principal Investigator (PI) separately to each cohort. The email included a quick note from the PI followed by a detailed invitation from the consultant to join a 1-hour long focus group. Focus groups were conducted at a time already allocated for regularly scheduled CLImates meetings.

Focus groups were conducted in December 2024 and January 2025. The findings presented here reflected participants' experiences half-way through the CLImates program (scheduled to end in April 2025).

The study was conducted with approval from University of Northern Colorado's institutional Review Board to ensure that it adhered to ethical standards in conducting research with people (protocol #2207041159).

Audiences

The audiences depicted below represent the three CLImates cohorts and a fourth comprising the student leaders. They are referred to as such all throughout the report.

Student cohort (n = 9)

The students were majoring in a range of disciplines, varying in how directly they focused on environment-related topics.

Faculty cohort (n = 9)

Similar to the first year, the nine faculty members represented different disciplinary backgrounds and described playing varying roles combining teaching and research at UNC.

Organizational members cohort (n = 8)

Individuals in this cohort were from local community organizations that focused on environmental and social issues, working with specific subgroups of the general public.

Student leadership (n = 3)

The student leaders took on similar roles in the project, focused on communications and coordination with the various cohorts involved in the program.

Participation for all audiences was voluntary and they could choose whether to join, and which questions to answer.

Analysis

The analysis for all groups examined how they had benefited from their interactions within and across cohorts, their learning about local climate priorities, and their future engagement and roles in COOLER. Each group's responses were analyzed and coded through an iterative process.

Similar to the first year, each group's responses were analyzed separately first. The main questions guiding the evaluation were used to organize the results. Responses of each group are presented as they address the main questions, identifying unique themes for each group as they emerged. This process aimed to provide a holistic picture of groups' experiences, rather than identify consensus, especially in the context of very small sample sizes (Malterud et al., 2016; Schreiber & Asner-Self, 2011).

Similar to last year, common themes across groups were discussed in the Implications section of the report, drawing inferences from the findings. To protect confidentiality of the participants, details of faculty and students' disciplinary backgrounds and organizational partners' work foci have not been described. Themes have been aggregated and generalized to retain the sentiments and thoughts expressed, while excluding identifying information. For the three student leaders, the number describing a specific theme was not included to protect their identity.

RESULTS

Most valuable impacts

Faculty appreciated the learning community around climate change

Faculty (n = 7) agreed that the biggest impact for them was being part of a community with shared interests around the topic of climate change. Those who elaborated (n = 5), appreciated learning new information, being connected to helpful faculty colleagues, especially to reduce their sense of isolation, increase their morale, and inspire their work. The opportunity to interact with organizational partners whose focus was climate change was also refreshing and exciting (n = 4). A couple of people anticipated future impacts in their work, either by informing their teaching or in meaningful action (unspecified) from current interactions. One person appreciated learning about the many approaches to address climate change impacts.

Student cohort members valued interacting with people with different viewpoints

Students described the value of engaging with others holding different perspectives to address climate change impacts (n = 3). One of them specifically appreciated being able to interact closely with the faculty PIs. Students (n = 3) described other specific ways they had been impacted, including being connected to people from whom to learn about concrete environmental actions, such as by supporting a specific project or disseminating information. Some students (n = 4) felt the resources that were shared were most beneficial, providing access to scientific information and helping them learn new content; they also appreciated being able to participate in climate focused events (e.g., air quality).

The COOLER Team hosts a table at a Climate Conversations Event at the Library Innovation Center in Greeley.

Student leaders gained professional skills

Student leaders benefited most by growing their professional capacity and gaining leadership, communication, and collaborative skills. This was a direct corollary of their unique roles, motivated by their knowledge of climate impacts and interest in action to tackle them.

Organizational partners connected with other local groups

The organizational partners (n = 5) most benefited from the connections made with colleagues in other organizations committed to addressing local environmental and related social issues. Individuals described feeling motivated, learning new information, expanding their mind by interacting with others holding views differing from their own, and even broadening the audiences for their work. One person mentioned feeling supported by the community of like-minded people that was being fostered.

Within cohort interaction

Faculty learned about multi-disciplinary approaches to climate change

Faculty further elaborated that they had appreciated learning from colleagues from multiple disciplines (n = 3). They enjoyed reflecting on their work, hearing others' unique take on the work, being able to bounce ideas off each other, and applying new perspectives to their own work. As a result, they were able to explore new collaborations (n = 2) and start considering their responsibility as local environmental stewards. One person mentioned how the learning community offered a level of support and accountability to be productive and develop a tangible project.

Students interacted with peers around the topic of climate change

Students (n = 3) appreciated being able to share their personal experiences and interest in climate change with peers, something they felt was not typically done in regular interactions with peers. This had allowed them to learn about experiences and perspectives that were different from their own; and engage with people who are not as motivated to address climate impacts.

Organizational partners learned about other organizations with similar interest

The organizational cohort members had greatly appreciated learning about other organizations that had shared interests in climate work (n = 4). The interactions provided the opportunity for knowledge and resource exchange, especially to understand each other's role locally, and appreciate specific community groups' needs. The exchanges also helped members consider ways in which they could collaborate with each other, including offering resources that might fill a gap.

Cross-cohort interactions

Faculty and student cohort interactions were limited

Faculty described their experiences in the CLimates program with student cohort members to be limited. Some had not interacted with students (n = 3) and wanted to engage more. They expressed that they would reach out to students when the need arose and that students were difficult to reach via email, especially from disciplines other than their own. One person described varying experiences with students during the initial in-person meeting (group discussions that were either good or one-sided, initiated by the faculty member) and wondered if they were intimidated in conversations with faculty. One person described ongoing

connections with students starting with the initial meeting, and following up on a one-on-one basis, and during theme meetings.

Student cohort members' description of interactions with faculty also suggested limited interaction (n = 3) that focused mostly on learning about climate change through specific disciplinary foci. One student had chatted with a faculty member who had incorporated lessons about climate change into their classroom curriculum, and others appreciated that faculty engaged students by learning through projects that demonstrated theory in practice.

Student cohort members (n = 3) described positive experiences with the COOLER faculty leaders. They appreciated how engaging and approachable the faculty leads were, their passion for the project, and their valuing student perspectives on climate work.

The student leaders were similarly effusive about their positive experiences with the faculty leads. They appreciated faculty members' expertise, guidance and mentorship, and their appreciation of students' leadership contributions.

Faculty and organizational cohort interactions varied

The faculty members who mentioned their interactions with the organizational partners described them to be limited to the theme team meetings (n =3). On the other hand, organizational partners (n = 4) described focused interactions with faculty members to exchange environment or climate-related expertise to their respective audiences. This included collaborations around classroom curricula and events, accessing cutting edge environmental science, and broadening their audiences.

Organizational and student cohort interactions were limited

The organizational partners described limited experiences interacting with students (n = 4). All but one of them found it difficult reaching them after initial interest in collaborative projects and confirming involvement in joint projects. One of them wondered if the timing (close to holiday season at the end of the year) was a barrier to student engagement, and if it may get easier after the holidays. Another appreciated learning about students' interests, including related to projects they wanted to join, during the initial in-person meeting (when students had expressed interest in a project idea suggested). Yet another had contacted students outside of the cohort meetings after the initial in-person meeting, but was unable to continue connecting with them.

Students described mixed experiences with the organizational cohort members. Some described the potential value of connecting with them (n = 3) including having access and being able to approach partners who were actively addressing local climate impacts. A couple of others expressed enthusiasm and aspirations about collaborating with organizational partners in the future on specific projects. Two others were a bit more apprehensive - one felt that differences in terminology used to describe required skills in a student job posting was a barrier to engagement; the other mentioned challenges in connecting with organizational cohort members.

Theme team meetings

Barring a couple of exceptions, all cohorts described their experiences of theme team meetings to be limited or challenging for various reasons. Overall, 2-4 people responded to this question in each cohort, a couple needing clarification on what the meetings entailed.

Faculty who described limited attendance in the themed meetings (n = 2) mentioned being unsure about how to incorporate the topics discussed into their classes, prioritizing project work, or wanting to attend more when their schedule permitted. One faculty member described that students during the theme team meetings were inspirational, expressing interest and

generating good ideas, which led to the faculty joining a student project. They described the theme team meetings as an “even field” where students could reach them easily.

Organizational partners described scheduling conflicts that prevented them from participating consistently (n = 4). One of them had hoped to engage with more students, and expressed disappointment about limited student attendance at a meeting. They also found the slide deck to learn about projects and select ones of interest was limited because there wasn't enough information about the project lead and their interests.

Students also expressed challenges joining the virtual meetings due to scheduling conflicts; they engaged more on the shared online platform for the CLImates programs.

COOLER CLImates participants celebrate the CLImates Kick-off event in September 2024.

Each cohort encountered different perspectives uniquely

Faculty members, while enthused about interacting with people holding differing perspectives on climate work, were cautious about the process of engaging in meaningful dialogue (n = 3). They acknowledged that it may be difficult to identify shared priorities to collaborate on, despite having overlapping higher level goals. They shared the need for a structured process to identify different levels of intersections to focus on, while being attentive to each other's distinct interests.

Organizational partners (n = 3) acknowledged they had not had conversations where differences in opinion emerged. In fact, one person shared that discussion of potential projects around topics of common interest had, by design, led to interactions with like-minded people.

Students on the other hand (n = 4), felt that different approaches to addressing climate change would help build skills to appreciate each other's unique take, despite the inevitable friction that may emerge. One student noted that discussions so far had been professional and collegial, where discussions were more informative about different experiences than prescriptive.

Student leaders described skills required to navigate different views on climate change. They felt that COOLER had helped them hone their own skills in communicating with others about climate change, while respecting other views.

Learning about climate change and its impacts

Faculty grew their understanding of how people address climate change impacts

Faculty members had expanded their understanding of the multiple approaches to address climate change, and its impact on human functioning (n = 2). One member appreciated learning about the emotional experiences that are deeply intertwined with learning about climate impacts on people and the rest of the non-human natural world. The other had a better sense of the diversity of perspectives that contribute to climate discourse and action, including those that shape misinformation.

Organizational partners learned about other groups tackling climate change

Organizational partners (n = 4) described awareness of different organizations and how they are tackling local climate impacts in their own ways. One of them further elaborated that they were better able to connect different kinds of climate-related work and the feedback loops across various societal systems. Another member emphasized that the project validated the multi-dimensional aspect of climate change and the interconnectedness between various environment-related phenomena.

Organizational partners grew their capacity to be climate stewards

Some organizational partners described how they had enhanced their individual capacity as climate stewards (n = 4). They described having a better understanding of the scope of local climate-related work and the needs of different audiences, being more motivated to leverage their own skills, being more strategic, and increasing their professional connections.

Student cohort members and student leaders grew their climate stewardship skills

Student cohort members had learned how to appreciate others' perspectives on climate change and ways to communicate about climate change (n = 2). They had also increased their capacity to be local climate stewards (n = 3) by developing a project to address impacts in Greeley or providing resources for an existing project, being able to make the topic more relatable to people, and igniting hope in oneself as part of the community.

Similarly, the student leaders appreciated learning about unique perspectives on climate change, social-emotional experiences from being impacted, and the many solutions possible. They had also built their skills to communicate in hopeful ways with the public and also gained a better understanding of how engaged and motivated local residents are.

At COOLER tabling events, UNC students respond to questions about how they hope the university will work to promote sustainability.

Perceptions of climate resilience

Cohort members' understanding of the term 'climate resilience' emphasized multiple connotations, including individuals' and groups' collective capacities to address climate resilience.

Organizational partners emphasized fostering a community with shared interests

Organizational partners (n = 3) described 'resilience' as community building in addition to strategic approaches, such as adaptation and mitigation, that could be taken to tackle climate change. Another person conceptualized it as people's ability to take action, describing how the project helped them better cope with the challenging and demoralizing work, by highlighting communities' work.

Students focused on individual capacity and infrastructure

Student cohort members (n = 3) also described the term as people’s skills and capacity (citing their own personal resilience and ability to adapt and overcome challenges) as well as the need to develop physical and natural infrastructure in places that will be damaged from extreme weather events.

Student leaders’ responses were similar to that of the student cohort members with some additional nuances. Apart from acknowledging people’s personal capacity building, they emphasized being prepared and proactive to tackle solutions and the need for collective capacity. They were also very mindful that the term had different meanings for people based on their experiences.

At a COOLER table at the Greeley Farmers Market, passersby share how they feel about climate change by placing a marble in a jar.

Impacts on current and future work

Faculty informed their teaching and research through lessons learned

Faculty cohort members (n = 3) had learned about new topics relevant to the lessons they taught, gained access to new information and resources that informed their classroom lessons, and developed ideas for a research project. One faculty member described a project their students worked on and how it helped develop skills and accountability.

Organizational partners expanded their organization's capacity

Organizational partners' work benefited (n = 3) from members connecting with other groups to be able to expand their organizational work locally, drawing in additional audiences, and fostering collaborations.

Students developed professional skills and were recognized as campus climate leaders

Student cohort members (n = 4) elaborated on the skills they developed. The skills related to communication to make climate change relatable to people, networking by interacting with faculty and organizational partners, learning to coordinate people by organizing meetings, and career development from being able to make elevator pitches about their work.

They also described positive experiences related to their university experiences (n = 4). These included expanding their social and professional network on campus, being seen as an advocate to address climate change, and also shifting how they consider applications of the knowledge they gain from conceptual topics.

Student members described impacts on their personal and professional lives. One person was more environmentally conscious, leading to and making personal choices to reduce their carbon impact. Others described how learning about tools to teach about climate change to different audiences would help them in their future career as a science educator.

Student leaders emphasized their skill and professional development

Student leaders described similar impacts stemming from their roles. They felt more confident in communicating about climate change, engaging with and supporting the CLImates cohorts as a result of their work on COOLER. They had grown their profile as leaders on campus and felt more connected to a community interested in tackling climate change locally, including through collaborations with professors and being in the know about other similar environmental efforts on campus.

Student leaders saw immediate benefits on their professional careers post-graduation. The CLImates experience expanded their options for potential future climate-focused employers, enhanced their marketability, and sparked further educational interests.

Future engagement with COOLER

Faculty cohort members (n = 2) hoped to develop collaborative projects and also access resources to continue to enhance their teaching. Similarly, organizational cohort members looked forward to advancing projects with students (n = 3). Students (n = 3) wanted to continue reading the COOLER newsletter, attend COOLER events, practice the skills they developed, and continue to grow the community. Student leaders too, were eager to stay connected with the COOLER community and continue collaborating with the many people engaged.

IMPLICATIONS FOR THE FUTURE

Fostering a learning community

In the second year of the COOLER project, the CLImates program demonstrated the evolution and growth of a learning community between UNC faculty, students, and local organizational partners. The interactions between and within the three cohorts were reminiscent of a learning 'ecosystem', where different place-based entities dynamically connect and sustain each other.

It built on the first year's work that focused on developing a learning community among UNC faculty, while initiating relationships with local organizations, CLImates expanded to initiate more engagement with UNC students and members from external organizations, comprising audiences interested in addressing local climate impacts and thus, advancing environmental and social welfare.

The cohort-based model resembled a community of practice (CoP) in action, designed to enable members to interact with each other, learn about members' expertise and interests, and in some cases, and apply the learning to inform their own or their organizations' work (Wenger, Trayner, & de Laat, 2011). The strongest interactions and learning occurred within cohorts comprising groups of peers with similar professional or academic roles. Consistently, within each cohort, faculty, students, and organizational partners appreciated being part of a supportive network to help them address local climate impacts through their distinct roles in Greeley.

At a CLImates workshop, participants share their visions for building a sustainable community.

Similar to the previous year, the CLimates program, and especially the cohort meetings, allowed members to interact with their peers to better understand each other's interests and potential contributions to take climate actions. The first phase of a CoP, was once again observed, characterized by *Immediate Value*, when people acknowledge the unique knowledge or experiences members contribute. Faculty appreciated learning about multi-disciplinary approaches to address climate change. Students similarly had learned about how different experiences impact people's understanding of climate change. Organizational partners had been introduced to new local groups with shared interests.

There was also indication that cohorts recognized the *Potential Value* of the interactions for their work. While cross-cohort interaction had been relatively limited, all cohorts acknowledged future opportunities for collaboration with members outside of their cohort. In fact, some faculty and organizational cohort members described how the knowledge, resources, exchanges, and collaboration had enhanced their professional work (i.e., teaching, research, organizational capacity building), indicating *Applied Value*. For students, this was manifest in how they became more visible climate stewards on campus. While the professional impacts for faculty and organizational partners were mostly informed by within cohort engagement, a few were also informed by cross-cohort interactions. This is promising for a newly initiated community of practice, comprising members with starkly distinct roles in Greeley with ingrained power differentials among them.

Growing current and future climate stewardship

CLimates had empowered the cohorts to be more effective climate stewards. Student cohort members, student leaders, and organizational partners described becoming more skilled and equipped climate stewards in Northern Colorado as a result of CLimates. Students especially were more confident in communicating and engaging with others and elevating their profile on campus. Student leaders anticipated professional benefits in the near future from the connections and skills they developed through the project. Organizational partners described how the lessons learned had benefited their organizations' climate capacity. While most students had not collaborated with faculty and organizational partners at the time of the focus groups, the latter foresaw the potential for deeper engagement, which will likely have more profound professional impacts on student cohorts.

Climate resilience is a collective endeavor

The sense of community fostered by CLimates was apparent in students' and organizational partners' understanding of 'climate resilience'. Personal growth was paramount to being able to learn with others and co-develop solutions to address climate priorities, including bolstering natural and built infrastructure. Members' felt that being part of a community helped enhance their capacity to cope (Swim, Geiger, Fraser, & Pletcher, 2017) and feel hopeful despite the challenges of climate change (Ojala, 2012).

COOLER CLimates students crafted origami flowers during a workshop on communicating climate change.

The CLimates program helped cohort members appreciate multiple approaches to tackling climate priorities, which was evident in appreciating that “climate resilience” would convey different meanings to different people, depending on their interests and priorities.

While faculty perspectives on this topic were unavailable, the findings above on multiple interpretations of ‘climate resilience’ are similar to those from the first year’s evaluation with faculty members and student leaders. It is expected that faculty, along with students and organizational partners will continue to think expansively about ‘climate resilience’ and inform their work accordingly.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made for future iterations of the COOLER project, building on the ones made at the end of the first year.

1. Continue to provide purposeful and regular opportunities for cross-cohort interactions to connect and learn deeply about each other’s work, including theme team meetings. Some suggestions for the theme team meetings are as follows:
 - a. Develop a retreat type opportunity (potentially at the start of the year’s work) for cohort members to learn about each other’s work and engage deeply. This would provide focused time to identify shared areas of interest and collaborative projects.
 - b. Strategize with cohort members to identify dates and times for the theme team meetings that meet members’ needs, and collaboratively identify workarounds for those whose schedules may not align.
 - c. Allocate more time for presenters to share their project so that other attendees can appreciate their focus, interests, and the support they need from collaborators. This would ultimately foster interest among members to collaborate with members from other cohorts.
2. Support faculty and organizational partners in connecting more effectively with students. This could be done by engaging the student leaders in identifying strategies to do more outreach with their peers and encouraging their active participation.
3. Continue to develop campus wide events to encourage informal interactions between organizational partners and the broader campus community. This would enable them to engage with more UNC faculty and students and broaden their organization’s work.

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